

Corrosion of IZOMER TT Glass Fiber Under Static Conditions In Distilled Water And In Borate Coolant Solution

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ABSTRACT

Large amounts of glass fibers are used as thermal insulation in nuclear power plants (NPPs). In the event of a loss of coolant accident (LOCA) [1–4] the insulation is mechanically destroyed by steam impact and drops to the bottom of the reactor containment, where it is immersed in the alkaline coolant liquid. According to alkali resistance of the commercially produced thermal fibrous insulations glass dissolution occurs, followed by later re-precipitation from the over-saturated solutions. A fraction of the fibers is also captured on the sump screen and thus prevents recirculation of the coolant in the emergency cooling system. Since the partially dissolved fibers can be mechanically destroyed (crushed), they can block the strainer causing failure of the emergency cooling system. In this situation the high head loss reaches a value that disables the operation of the pumps. The above effect of strainer blocking can be dramatically enhanced by strengthening of the fiber bed by the re-precipitated matter. Therefore study of the kinetics and thermodynamics of glass dissolution is needed for correct modeling of the process and its consequences on the operability of the emergency systems [5]. Chemical durability of glass with the composition of glass fibrous insulation IZOMER TT commonly used in nuclear power plants reactor containment was tested by static leaching tests at 70°C, 80°C, and 90°C. Distilled water and borate coolant solution were used as corrosive media. The semiempirical kinetic model based on the Aagaard Helgeson kinetic equation was proposed and qualified. Proposed model enables prediction of glass dissolution kinetics for various time–temperature schedules proposed for different Loss of Coolant Accident scenarios.

Keywords: Glass corrosion, LOCA, Glass fiber insulation, Coolant solution, Glass grain, Kinetics.

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